

ISic2717

I.Sicily inscription 2717

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

marble (blue)

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museum or catacomb Antiquarium

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---έ]νθάδε

2. [---]ις ἔζησεν

3. [ἔτη ---]

Apparatus

Text after Griesheimer 1996

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645137

PHI 333384

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques*

relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. At 1996.0804

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum.* At 46.1288

Griesheimer, M. 1996. Nouvelles inscriptions funéraires de la catacombe Saint-Jean. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana.* 72: 115-132. At 124 no.8 fig.8

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